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The Long Road to Regulation – Regulation on Cabin Air Quality

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Abstract

Purpose: This work provides an overview, from a Consumer perspective, on how the problem of Cabin Air Quality is being addressed through the development of an International Standard and hard laws. The author is neither a scientist, engineer nor pilot, but has had to engage with each of those disciplines and determine how a better outcome can be achieved for ordinary airline passengers and the air that they breathe. The paper concludes on the conflicts that arise from the development of standards against the growing imperative of hard-law creation. This growing imperative is set against the numerous conflicts between a desire to create a safer aircraft environment and agenda; it begs the question; are we still standing at a crossroads or is a new realisation dawning?

Methodology: The author's extensive experience in the work of standardisation, political consumer lobbying, drafting legal solutions and dealing with direct Consumer contact, across two continents, has been critically examined to provide an overview and analysis of the current or potential benefits for Consumers.

Findings: The issue of contaminated Cabin Air has developed an International 'Standards' circus, where politics, commercial politics and the possibility of solutions constantly challenge or its methodology and outcomes are challenged. There is a difficulty in a rule-based Standards-making system that fails to adequately deploy methodology and define adequately what constitutes a consensus. This paper continues to highlight those difficulties where the whole question of aviation standardisation remains in a state of flux. The alternative of a hard-law solution is not only on the horizon but is being developed by aviation-user activists.

Limitations: This paper is limited to the work, view and opinions of one independent Consumer Campaigner. But the subject matter is also limited by the scant attention paid by many European Consumer Organisations to this work. Current EU Standardisation Regulation only recognises Consumer 'Establishment' Organisations.

Practical Implications: This paper has important political and methodology implications for the future of European Standardisation, along with the range of standards created by the European Regulator (EASA) and the potential for their work on contaminated Cabin Air. It also raises important questions about the state and status of Aviation Regulation in the EU.

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Review process: Editorial review.

Social Implications: The commentary in this paper has the potential to alert the EU Consumer Organisation Industry as to the complexity of issues on contaminated Cabin Air and the process of achieving Consumer protections either through hard-law or soft-law. It also has the potential to raise awareness amongst Consumer globally as to the nature of Cabin Air Quality.

Value and Originality: The originality of this paper is founded in the experience of its author and its ability to highlight key issues that have the potential to lead to a solution to the long-standing problem of contaminated air within aircraft.

Keywords (ACA Component Head)

cabin air quality, aircraft, travel, holidays, flight, consumer rights, consumers, air passengers, activism, aviation, aviation regulator, standards

1 Introduction

I would like to thank the organisers of this conference for their kind invitation extended to me to speak at today's event. My presentation is entitled 'The long road to Regulation'; that is Regulation on Cabin Air Quality. The entry point for my role in this important work came in 2006, when I first came into contact with a group of passengers, affected by a fume event on their flight down to Florida. From that contact, I met and spoke with many passengers from other flights and spoke with some remarkable aircrew, all clearly affected from their journeys or roles in the workplace through exposure to fumes within the aircraft environment.

By 2012, I was engaged with a cohort of pilots, cabin crew and trade unions where we set about challenging the perceived wisdom contained within an existing European Standard.

Our challenge was successful, and this led to the creation of a new European Standard proposal, where all the principal players from across Europe came together to begin the task of drafting a new Standard, where all voices were heard.

By the end of 2020, the draft European Standard (prEN 17436) was ready¹.

2 A One-Side Consensus?

However, we encountered some difficulties in the end-process, which was fostered by external players who had cried foul, complaining that the new draft was onerous, lacked proof of applicability and had no consensus.

These same challenges continue to this very day against the demoted text of the draft Standard which now exists as a European Technical Report (CEN/TR 17904)². It is important to remember, that in the face of good provenance and due diligence of the Standards Committee, the compromise to a Technical Report presents a document which has no obligations nor requirements.

This constant battle to agree text by consensus and produce something of value is a good example of us having to deal with the myths claimed against the reality.

The myth or myths are contained within the challenges that were made, when the reality can be found in the records of the Committee which demonstrate robust debates, active engagement by all parties and that all-important consensus in text and decisions made.

It requires constant vigilance, and we would hope in the face of these continuing challenges, there will be a growing confidence in the standards-making processes we deployed, along with robustness and support from within the European Standards body.

1 <https://www.eurocockpit.eu/news/support-new-standard-cabin-air-quality>, <https://perma.cc/4BMC-J5KY>, <https://perma.cc/XK7Q-LU6Z>

2 <https://www.etuc.org/en/pressrelease/airline-industry-must-implement-new-cabin-air-standards>, <https://perma.cc/K2RW-4J9S>

3 The Rise of Formal Regulation

In the United States, there is a slow but also a steady progress being made against the backdrop of an equally slow but advancing science and knowledge.

But on the opposite side of the coin there lurks, not just in the USA, a growing trend against consensus – as we have found, it is the challenge everything – accept nothing strategy!

As we have experienced in our work, there is a clear but generic unwillingness to accept Aviation Users evidence, sometimes citing that evidence as ‘subjective’ opinion, with a seemingly gradual retreat into echo chambers where activist voices are not apparently heard nor indeed present.

The irony of this is that as Aviation Users present their evidence, collective voices rejecting such evidence conveniently forget that the Aviation Industry has created a slew of globally published patents which clearly spell out the cabin air quality problem along with their proposed solutions.

As we look to this Global Standards Caravan, along with a growing but apparent unwillingness to engage and work together, and I have to say this is also evident from some of the Executive Agencies or Directorates in Europe (a complaint often made by colleagues), it has left a substantial number of activists wondering if the creation of Standards is now past its sell-by-date?

It is perhaps not surprising that after many years hard work and engagement, it was inevitable that legislators would recognise the need for hard-law against discretionary Standards or the soft-law environment.

As you will be hearing from Senator Blumenthal in this conference, and I have no wish to steal his thunder, the US Congress has demonstrated that they are to be the first out of the traps to create the first draft hard-law through its Cabin Air Safety Bill (now an Act, passed in 2023)³.

Whilst we shall hear from Senator Blumenthal about its creation and methodology, it is perhaps worth dwelling on the words of Representative Garamendi who in supporting the provisions of the Bill stated:

“All Americans have the right to expect safe clean air when they fly”⁴.

I believe that his sentiment is easily transferred to the global flying population which was indeed uppermost in our minds throughout all our European Standards work and engagement.

4 The Construction of Regulation

If the American Act progresses speedily through its implementation phase, it has in my opinion, the potential to offer a considerable marketing opportunity for airlines and manufacturers in America, whatever about the bonus of delivering a potentially safer aircraft cabin environment.

I have noted some of the key features of the American Act which includes, mandated training across those who work within Aviation operations, a requirement for the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA)⁵ to record, monitor and report ‘fume’ or other cabin air quality incidents, a mandate is also given to the FAA which empowers them to investigate but with some concern I note that it provides them with a discretion with regards to those investigations. Importantly the Act will require aircraft operators to install monitors, primarily for Carbon Monoxide (CO) and for hydraulic fluids.

I can certainly get behind this Act but remember, I come from a completely different jurisdiction, which has a different way of looking at Regulation-making. From a personal perspective, as I examined the then Bill, I would have liked to have seen the Precautionary Principle embedded within, along with a definitive passenger right to know (we

3 <https://www.congress.gov/bill/118th-congress/senate-bill/615>

4 <https://garamendi.house.gov/media/press-releases/garamendi-blumenthal-reintroduce-bill-protect-airline-passengers-crew>

5 <https://www.faa.gov>

can see those elements incorporated into the European Technical Report I have previously referred to). That said, and despite its critics, this Act comes at the end of a poor and disjointed Standards process, coupled with poor actions from Global regulators, but, what it does, is to potentially change the dynamic on Cabin Air Quality.

In Europe, in the midst of general standards-making, we can also see the plethora of Regulator Standards, stemming from hard-aviation-law, but which contain no legislative obligations.

There is currently an interesting debate to be had on their legal status, when measured against the recent 'James Elliot' Standards case from the European Court of Justice (ECJ) and the turmoil that it created for European-Standards⁶. In considering the James Elliot case we should perhaps not forget the Beauty Salon Services Standard⁷ which was challenged within the standards-making process, both on professional and public health concerns: "a claim of defective standard which revolved, in essence, around the distinction between client (beauty salons) and patient (medical practitioners), challenging thereby the safety and – later on - hygiene provisions of the standard". This latter case could be an important tool in the armoury of challenging a published or soon to be published Standard, particularly if there are public health concerns⁸.

Whatever the construction of hard and soft law, for those of us challenging the status-quo, it seems logical, that in the face of reducing recognition of our views, engagement, or progress, in making our challenges to increase obligations in soft law, we have had to question our own commitment to support the light-touch regulatory approach when perhaps formal Regulation presents stronger opportunities.

In rising to those challenges and opportunities, for the last two years, colleagues and I have been working on drafting an over-arching EU Regulation on Cabin Air Quality.

Our work is almost complete and, in some respects, our draft Bill mirrors some of the key features of the US Act. We have created an extensive preamble, (not uncommon within EU Directives or Regulation), along with delivering a tighter scope to our draft Bill. We have increased the regulatory oversight so delivering greater enforcement powers. We confront (as many aviation patents do), the nature of the unique environment of the aircraft, so moving the narrative away from the distraction of ground-based indoor environments. We lay out the comprehensive range of chemical compounds said to be reliably found within aircraft and obligations on manufacturers and airlines. Training and education feature as does the all-important requirement on data reporting and analysis.

Importantly we import the Precautionary Principle⁹ (as found in many EU Directives and Regulations), as opposed to the ALARP system ('as low as reasonably practicable'), the latter relying heavily on an 'engineering' discretion and a reliance on a heavy costs/benefits analysis. Indeed, through this engagement there are those who resist the premise of the Precautionary Principle claiming that it creates an obligation to deliver a zero-risk environment, which of course it does not.

In considering and drafting such a provision regarding 'engineering' discretion, it is important to make clear that this is not to denigrate nor demote the undeniable value that 'engineers' deliver to society, but it is against applying that same discretion, widely found in Standards and indeed Aviation Laws or Standards; its inclusion provides in my opin-

6 <https://bit.ly/4b98Kf2> – This case that came before the European Court of Justice in 2017, which declared that mandated/harmonised Standards, attached to European Regulation, should also be considered as law and capable of use in private proceedings. This decision had a profound effect on the Standards world causing a radical rethink on mandates, stakeholders and the EU single market. There was also some palpable reticence from Companies who had been given up-to-that-point-in-time free-rein to define their operations and the standards for their industry or products without a wider engagement. On reflection I have noted that the Treaties of the EU provide for a division of labour and competency for the benefit of the Union and the Single Market amongst the Institutions and its agencies. One competency is Aviation. EASA (the European Aviation Safety Agency – the Regulator) has been given that competency by the EU to make regulation. Therefore, the 'standards' attached to formal regulation, those being Certification Specification's (CS's), Acceptable Means of Compliance (AMC's) & (Alternative Means of Compliance (AltMoC's), could therefore be logically considered to be mandated and therefore harmonised; is there a potential possibility that they could be classed as formal law, with all their apparent imperfections?

7 <https://www.top-normy.cz/users/files/procesy-tn/CEN-CENELEC-Refit.pdf>

8 That was certainly the case in 2020 when one sector made clear that the then drafted Standard would be considered by them to be acting contrary to the Public Health interests of EU Citizens. That challenge never materialised, but it remains an interesting possibility for those from the Aviation User cohort when presented perhaps with an EU Industry-driven Standard, which could be said to be acting contrary to the Public Health interests of Aircrew and EU Citizens?

9 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2000:0001:FIN:en:PDF>

ion, a false safety net for engineers in a complex world of science, technology and legal issues. So to include such a wide discretion in 21st Century Aviation Standards (which some refer to as ‘regulation’), flies in the face of that ever changing science, technology, knowledge and uncertainty. With such uncertainty we need a stronger more universally accepted methodology as we find in the Precautionary Principle and to remove the ‘subjective’ discretionary language as found in current EU Aviation Standards¹⁰.

Given the rapidly changing debate on the Climate Crisis and Sustainability we have also built Sustainability into our draft Regulation reflecting the key features of EU Policy (Good Health & Well-being & Sustainable Technology being two examples¹¹).

Another important feature contained within our draft Regulation is the creation of a true and inclusive Consultative Committee which delivers a strong democratisation of the new processes contained within our draft regulation, which interestingly, we see a similar discussion on democratisation¹² being discussed in EU Standards-making.

5 Conclusion

I believe that years of hard work and some disappointment has brought us to a yet another set of crossroads.

There is a clear and evident difficulty with Standards either created through transnational bodies or executive agencies.

As we have discovered, we have had to navigate and to an extent compromise on political and commercial cultures and on occasions, with behaviours. There is an important question or consideration about the hierarchy of compromise where I have concluded that health concerns must come first. That is not to say that current engagement in standards-making is wrong or a waste of time, it is but one venue where we can present and persuade the validity of our arguments. But, if the receivers of those arguments look away or reject our proposals, then we must also fully embrace the formal regulatory route; it is our duty to do so.

As the world of 2006 is now far behind my activism on this matter, the road ahead is fast changing. It now seems clearer than ever that we are on the cusp of real solutions that will change the conversation on causation whatever about any claims that it will increase potential litigation – this will in my opinion, hasten changes in the regulatory environment. Equally, as frustration with the standards-making process grows, and democratisation takes root, this advancing debate will supplant new processes, new dialogues & hopefully safer environments for aircrew and passengers.

The burning question now remains:

“Will the Aviation Industry continue to resist from their safe echo chambers, or will they return and once again rise to the challenges ahead and meet Aviation Users on that famous standards consensus bridge?”

10 https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/cs-25_amendment_25.pdf - Search for ‘engineering operational judgement’ to see the full range of references throughout this document

11 <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/at-a-glance/sustainability>

12 <https://ecostandard.org/wp-content/uploads/2018-06-11-The-use-of-standards-in-legislation-and-policies-ECOS-discussion-paper.pdf>

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About the Author

Frank Brehany. I am a dual-Citizen, one of which delivers a long-standing European Citizenship. I am a medically retired Police-Officer and qualified in 1997 as a practising Solicitor, working initially in formal legal practice, this eventually led to ownership and management of a National Consumers Organisation. My interests in Law covers not just Consumer Law, but also the problems found within Consumer Contracts, European Law, Human Rights and National and cross-border solutions to Consumer problems. I have extensive media experience, and comment on Legal issues for Consumers, Travel Trends and the Travel related problems experienced by Consumers.

I retired from formal legal practice in 2023 and my status is now recorded as a non-practising solicitor. I nonetheless continue to maintain, through legal training, my knowledgebase, which helps me in my advocacy on broader Consumer questions and to help develop solutions within the Standards-making and Political environments. I have never been a member of any political party or grouping and I voluntarily subscribe to the Nolan Principles for Standards in Public Life. In this work I am entirely self-funded.

My past legal and now activism work has always been about the day-to-day Consumer or Victim-related issues, but now I work in arguing both practically and politically for change on Cabin Air Quality. I also advocate for Human Rights issues in Ireland. I have published a book for Consumers to raise awareness of this issue: ‘Gaspers: Clean Air for Passengers?’¹³; a second edition will be available at the end of 2024. Webpage: <http://FrankBrehany.com>.

Title page of first edition.

13 <https://search.worldcat.org/en/title/1262374110>